

Path Towards Effective Regulations to Protect the Night

Plenary Lecture

Yana Yakushina¹

DOI:

Abstract: Recently, light pollution started to gain more and more political attention at different regulatory levels, spanning from local to international. The reasons for this are growing research, indicating significant adverse impacts of artificial light at night (ALAN), energy efficiency concerns and the protection of astronomical observations. These triggers led several countries across the world to adopt regulatory measures aimed at mitigating light pollution, protecting the night and promoting more responsible lighting practices. Despite growing momentum, regulatory approaches remain highly fragmented. Legal frameworks vary substantially across jurisdictions, and many still lack comprehensive or enforceable provisions. These inconsistencies create significant gaps that weaken both the enforceability and the overall effectiveness of measures aimed at reducing light pollution. Additionally, limited coordination between local, national, and international actors further constrains progress. In light of these challenges, there is a pressing need for more coherent and harmonized action. A unified approach could considerably enhance the impact of regulatory efforts while still allowing flexibility for local circumstances. The presentation offers a reflection on how light pollution and the protection of the night should be framed within regulatory frameworks and provides examples of the current state of regulations worldwide. It explores practical questions concerning the legal framing of light pollution: whether it ought to be recognized as a form of pollution, whether the night can be regarded as part of nature, and which regulatory approaches are likely to be most effective in safeguarding the nocturnal environment. The presentation concludes with practical recommendations for enhancing regulatory effectiveness without requiring major legislative reform, which may otherwise encounter resistance from governments at various levels.

Keywords: light pollution; legal framework; laws.

Corresponding Author: yayakushina@gmail.com

¹Ghent University, Belgium